

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340236781>

Antiviral properties of Elderberry

Preprint · March 2020

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12312.55043

CITATIONS

0

READS

1,302

1 author:

Domina Petric

UHC Split

156 PUBLICATIONS 2 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Perspective article: using a table of medications for counting pills in caregiving to elderly dementia patients with polytherapy who live alone [View project](#)

Safety in traffic. Physician 's perspective [View project](#)

Antiviral properties of Elderberry

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT: *Sambucus nigra* products (Sambucol) have antiviral properties against different strains of influenza virus. Sambucol Elderberry Extract and its formulations activate the healthy immune system by increasing inflammatory cytokine production. Standardized elderberry liquid extract possesses antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive bacteria of *Streptococcus pyogenes* and group C and G *Streptococci*, and the Gram-negative bacterium *Branhamella catarrhalis* in liquid cultures. *Sambucus Formosana* Nakai stem ethanol extract displayed the strong anti-HCoV-NL63 (human coronavirus NL63) potential.

Sambucus nigra L. products (Sambucol) are based on a standardized black elderberry extract. They are natural remedies with antiviral properties, especially against different strains of influenza virus. Sambucol was shown to be effective *in vitro* against 10 strains of influenza virus.

In a double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomized study conducted by Barak and coworkers (2001), Sambucol reduced the duration of flu symptoms to 3-4 days. Convalescent phase serum showed a higher antibody level to influenza virus in the Sambucol group, than in the control group. The production of inflammatory cytokines was tested using blood-derived monocytes from 12 healthy human donors. Adherent monocytes were separated from PBL and incubated with different Sambucol preparations i.e., Sambucol Elderberry

Extract, Sambucol Black Elderberry Syrup, Sambucol Immune System and Sambucol for Kids. Production of inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 beta, TNF-alpha, IL-6, and IL-8) was significantly increased, mostly by the Sambucol Black Elderberry Extract (2-45 fold), as compared to LPS, a known monocyte activator (3.6-10.7 fold).

The most striking increase was noted in TNF-alpha production (44.9 fold).

Authors concluded from this study that, in addition to its antiviral properties, Sambucol Elderberry Extract and its formulations activate the healthy immune system by increasing inflammatory cytokine production¹.

Conducted by Professor Fariba Deghani, Dr Golnoosh Torabian and Dr Peter Valtchev as part of the ARC Training Centre for the Australian Food Processing

Industry, the study showed that compounds from elderberries can directly inhibit the influenza virus's entry and replication in human cells, and can help strengthen a person's immune response to the virus.

The phytochemicals from the elderberry juice were shown to be effective at stopping the virus infecting the cells, but they were even more effective at inhibiting viral propagation at later stages of the influenza cycle when the cells had already been infected with the virus. The team also found that the elderberry's antiviral activity can be attributed to its anthocyanidin compounds, phytonutrients responsible for giving the fruit its vivid purple colouring².

In the study conducted by Krawitz and coworkers (2011) it was shown that a standardized elderberry liquid extract possesses antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive bacteria of *Streptococcus pyogenes* and group C and G *Streptococci*, and the Gram-negative bacterium *Branhamella catarrhalis* in liquid cultures. The liquid extract also displays an inhibitory effect on the propagation of human pathogenic influenza viruses³.

Elderberry extract from fruit and flowers appears to show some inhibitory effect against many microorganisms including those found as nosocomial pathogens such

as MRSA, HIV, *Mycoplasmae*, IBV coronavirus (infectious bronchitis virus, a pathogenic chicken coronavirus), and influenza (and its bacterial super-infections). These effects may be stronger *in vivo* than *in vitro*. Elderberry is also shown to have potential as an ingredient in a hospital disinfectant for which *in vitro* trials are sufficient. The author of the systematic review, Wermig-Morgan Julia proposed that elderberry should also be tested on SARS and other novel coronaviruses such as COVID-19⁴.

Human coronavirus NL63 (HCoV-NL63), one of the main circulating HCoVs worldwide, causes respiratory tract illnesses like runny nose, cough, bronchiolitis and pneumonia. *Sambucus Formosana* Nakai, a species of elderberry, is a traditional medicinal herb with anti-inflammatory and antiviral potential. The study conducted by Weng and coworkers (2019) investigated the antiviral activity of *Sambucus Formosana* Nakai stem ethanol extract and some phenolic acid constituents against HCoV-NL63. The extract was less cytotoxic and concentration-dependently increased anti-HCoV-NL63 activities, including cytopathicity, sub-G1 fraction, virus yield (IC₅₀ = 1.17 µg/ml), plaque formation (IC₅₀ = 4.67 µg/ml) and virus attachment (IC₅₀ = 15.75 µg/ml). Among the phenolic

acid constituents in *Sambucus Formosana* Nakai extract, caffeic acid, chlorogenic acid and gallic acid sustained the anti-HCoV-NL63 activity that was ranked in the following order of virus yield reduction: caffeic acid ($IC_{50} = 3.54 \mu M$) > chlorogenic acid ($IC_{50} = 43.45 \mu M$) > coumaric acid ($IC_{50} = 71.48 \mu M$). Caffeic acid significantly inhibited the replication of HCoV-NL63 in a cell-type independent manner, and specifically blocked virus attachment ($IC_{50} = 8.1 \mu M$). The results revealed that *Sambucus Formosana* Nakai stem ethanol extract displayed the strong anti-HCoV-NL63 potential. Caffeic acid could be the vital component with anti-HCoV-NL63 activity⁵.

Results of the study conducted by Chen and coworkers demonstrated that *S. nigra* extract can inhibit IBV (infectious bronchitis virus, a pathogenic chicken coronavirus) at an early point in infection, probably by rendering the virus non-infectious. Authors also suggest that future studies using *S. nigra* extract to treat or prevent IBV or other coronaviruses are warranted⁶.

CONCLUSION

Sambucus nigra products (Sambucol) have antiviral properties against different strains of influenza virus. Sambucol Elderberry Extract and its formulations activate the healthy immune system by increasing inflammatory cytokine production. Standardized elderberry liquid extract possesses antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive bacteria of *Streptococcus pyogenes* and group C and G *Streptococci*, and the Gram-negative bacterium *Branhamella catarrhalis* in liquid cultures. *Sambucus Formosana* Nakai stem ethanol extract displayed the strong anti-HCoV-NL63 (human coronavirus NL63) potential.

REFERENCES

1. Barak V, Halperin T, Kalickman I. The effect of Sambucol, a black elderberry-based natural product on the production of human cytokines: I. Inflammatory cytokines. *Eur Cytokine Netw.* 2001;12(2):290-6.
2. Torabian G, Valtchev P, Qayyum A, Dehghani F. Anti-influenza activity of elderberry (*Sambucus nigra*). *Journal of Functional Foods.* 2019;54:353.
3. Krawitz C, Mraheil MA, Stein M, et al. Inhibitory activity of a standardized elderberry liquid extract against clinically-relevant human respiratory bacterial pathogens and influenza A and B viruses. *BMC Complement Altern Med.* 2011;11:16.
4. Wermig-Morgan J. Elderberry is anti-bacterial, anti-viral and modulates the immune system: anti-bacterial, anti-viral and immunomodulatory non-clinical (in-vitro) effects of elderberry fruit and flowers (*Sambucus nigra*): a systematic review. 2020. Retrieved from (27-03-2020) https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339237008_Elderberry_is_anti-bacterial_anti-viral_and_modulates_the_immune_system_anti-bacterial_anti-viral_and_immunomodulatory_non-clinical_in-vitro_effects_of_elderberry_fruit_and_flowers_Sambucus_nigra_a_sy
5. Weng JR, Lin CS, Lai HC, et al. Antiviral activity of *Sambucus Formosana* Nakai ethanol extract and related phenolic acid constituents against human coronavirus NL63. *Virus Res.* 2019;273:197767.
6. Chen C, Zuckerman DM, Brantley S, et al. *Sambucus nigra* extracts inhibit infectious bronchitis virus at an early point during replication. *BMC Vet Res.* 2014;10:24.